

The HuT

Risk Management Plan

Deliverable D7.3

DEVELOPED WITHIN

WP7 Coordination and Management, T7.3 Monitoring and reporting

AUTHORS

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1. Technical references

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- * PU = Public
PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

1.1. Document history

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2.1. List of Tables

Table 1: Representatives of Consortium Partners at General Assembly **Error. Il segnalibro non è definito.**

2.2. List of Figures

None.

3. Executive summary

This deliverable establishes The Hut's risk management procedures, necessary to guarantee the project's success.

It covers policies and methods for identifying and managing unusual project deviation causes that could affect the project goals.

The Coordinator will ensure that the risk mitigation and contingency measures provided in this plan are met if needed.

4. Introduction

The goal of the **The Hut Risk Management Plan** is to increase the probability of the project success by identifying potential challenging tasks early and envisaging mitigation measures to avoid or reduce the probability of negative occurrence.

This plan lists the elements that have been identified as having the potential to affect how the project activities are carried out. This strategy also specifies how the risks will be mitigated and their projected effects.

This report is organized into a general overview of risk management for the The Hut project as a whole and a more in-depth discussion of risk management at the level of work packages.

The HuT will employ innovative disaster risk reduction solutions, accounting for the potential variations induced by climate change. This will involve integrating and leveraging best practices and successful multi-disciplinary experiences that have been recently developed within various territorial contexts by leading European research groups, institutions, and stakeholders, to deal with extreme climate events. The project's main ambition beyond the state of the art is to promote the "best set" of trans-disciplinary risk management tools and approaches that could be adopted and used extensively across Europe, in as many situations as possible. The activities of the project will be developed considering the following main critical dimensions: trans-disciplinarity, systemic risk, co-production, cross-fertilization, transferability, and long-term legacy.

A set of ten demonstrators will constitute a multi-hazard arena wherein possible disastrous events associated with climate extremes will be dealt with jointly by representatives of the scientific and technical communities, practitioners, policy-makers and local communities. The events associated to climate extremes that will be considered in this project are: forest fires, including wildland urban interface fires; meteorological/hydrological/agricultural droughts, including associated water shortage; heatwaves; weather-induced landslides, including debris flows; fluvial and pluvial floods; storms, including heavy rain, hail, thunderstorms, and storm surges. The HuT will mainly focus on the prevention and preparedness phases of the disaster risk management cycle, explicitly considering climate change scenarios and integrating the proposed set of solutions, for the various events considered, over short- (from days to several months) and long-term (from years to decades) time horizons.

5. Roles and responsibility

This section lists and discusses the roles within the project regarding risk management.

5.1. Coordinator

In addition to managing the project's organizational, legal, and financial aspects, the coordinator is in charge of upholding all commitments and responsibilities to the European Commission. Throughout the project's duration, he monitors the risk response process.

5.2. Project Management Team (PMT)

The PMT consists of: Project Coordinator Michele Calvello (UNISA), deputy-Coordinator Guido Rianna (CMCC), Project Manager Alfonso Rossi Filangieri (UNISA), and WP leaders Jo-Ting Huang-Lachmann (HEREON; WP1 leader) and Carina Fearnley (UCL; WP2 leader).

The PMT shall monitor the effective and efficient implementation of the Project and will support the Coordinator in the risk management.

5.3. Scientific Coordination Team (SCT)

In The HuT a Scientific Coordination Team (SCT), comprising the PC and all the other WP leaders, will monitor progress of the project in terms of achievement of objectives and milestones.

Among the others, the SCT is in charge identify, assess, mitigate, and communicate potential risks and relevant issues during the project life and set the editorial and security standards for the project deliverables, to ensure the quality and security of the project's outputs.

5.4. WP Leaders

The WP Leaders must deal with the specific risks for the deliverables and milestones related to the WP they are leading. They should update the Management Team and guarantee the risk identification and management. If any new risks arose, the PMT should be informed so that the risk table can be updated.

6. Risk Management

6.1. Risk identification and assessment

Several potential dangers and their countermeasures were identified throughout the proposal preparation phase and updated in the grant agreement. These are mentioned in Table “Critical risks & risk management strategy”.

During the project execution phase, newly potential identified risks will be reported. The focus will be on:

- Deliverable status
- Milestone fulfillment
- WP schedules and interaction between WP

The Risk Register includes the recording following assessment of the probability and impact of identified risks, measured against a matrix of High, Medium or Low, ranking them in order and establishing appropriate prioritisation and mitigation measures. The ‘likelihood’ and ‘impact’ risk level descriptions are the following.

LIKELIHOOD of risk level descriptions:

Low A ‘Low’ likelihood of risk to project The HuT indicates that the risk is unlikely to occur but requires regular monitoring.

Medium A ‘Medium’ likelihood of risk to project The HuT indicates that the risk is likely to occur and requires regular monitoring and review.

High A ‘High’ likelihood of risk to project The HuT indicates that the risk is highly likely to occur and requires rigorous and regular review.

SEVERITY of risk level descriptions:

Low A ‘Low’ impact of risk to project The HuT indicates that the risk will be unlikely to disrupt project progress but requires monitoring. and review.

Medium A ‘Medium’ impact of risk to project The HuT indicates that the risk is likely to disrupt project progress and action is required.

High A ‘High’ impact of risk to project The HuT indicates that the risk is highly likely to disrupt project progress and requires urgent action.

6.2. Risk monitoring

In order to update the risk table and determine the applicability of the tools, it is the duty of all the partners to inform the Coordinator on the status of the risks and mitigation actions, and possible new risk. Risk exposure will be reviewed by the PMT and modified as necessary.

Any additional concerns discovered by a partner will be examined in the same way as those on the first risk list before being added to the register.

7. Table of risks

Table 1: List of critical risks and proposed mitigation measures

#	Description	WP	Mitigation Measures
1	Lack of political commitment from the local authorities in the demonstrators, e.g., due to new elections (L: low, I: high)	WP1, WP3	Engage more with local communities, private sectors, and citizens for bottom-up implementation. Alternatively, find a new Demonstrator in a similar context in the same country to engage and upscale to further regions, and replicate the actions in the original Demonstrator.
2	Pandemic like situation hindering face-to-face stakeholders' engagement and interaction (L: medium, I: low)	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7	The HuT consortium and demonstrators are all equipped with digital tools for communications. Consortium partners and stakeholders in demonstrators will be provided free access to all the telecommunication software and tools to ensure continuous interactions.
3	Lack of community engagement (L:low, I: high)	WP1, WP2	Work with local leaders and agencies to build trust with local communities and build a collaborative relationship.
4	Unable to engage with vulnerable groups (L: medium, I: low)	WP2, WP6	Work with local community organisations to represent the needs of the vulnerable groups.
5	Language barriers in communication, particularly with the public (L: low, I: medium)	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP5, WP6	The scientific leaders of each demonstrator will be proactive in liaising the English-speaking international partnership with the local language-speaking communities. If needed, local partners will aid the dialogue with the public.
6	Characteristics of extreme climate risk preclude innovative insurance solutions (L: medium, I: low)	WP3	Other innovative financial products, e.g., resilience bonds, will become the focus of this activity.
7	Significant delay in the implementation of IoT monitoring systems (L: medium, I: medium)	WP4	The design and implementation of IoT sensors, by partners with significant expertise on this topic, will explicitly focus on reducing empty times that could negatively impact the deployment of these activities.
8	Not enough data in the demonstrators to test and validate models (L: medium, I: medium)	WP4	Exploit freely available datasets, e.g., Copernicus initiatives. Involve local stakeholders to find new useful datasets.

#	Description	WP	Mitigation Measures
9	Reduced participation in Local/International DRR nexus Forums (L: low, I: high)	WP1, WP5	Involve stakeholders in the demonstrators since the very beginning of the project. Capitalize existing networks of the partners to create links between The HuT and a large audience of potential stakeholders. Encourage stakeholders to take ownership of local Forums' sections.
10	Lack of interest for field visits (L: low, I: medium)	WP5	Clearly communicate the benefits of this action for a proper transfer process. Promote the activity in the Forums.
11	Lack of interest for the HuT activities (L: low, I: high)	WP6	Partners with consolidated expertise in dissemination and communication activities will deploy initiatives to target groups and effectively involve stakeholders.
12	Limited networking activities (L: low, I: high)	WP6	Partners with key positions in established international networks and projects will act to liaise The HuT with these initiatives. A legacy advisory panel will be created.
13	Partner leaving the consortium (L: low, I: medium)	WP7	For each activity, more than one partner is involved. The consortium is formed with redundant skills and responsibilities.
14	Inadequate quality of deliverables or delays in milestones (L: low, I: medium)	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5, WP6, WP7	A scientific coordination team, led by the project coordinator, will constantly monitor the progress of the project in terms of achievement of objectives and milestones, and it will ensure the quality and security of the project's outputs.
15	Temporary or permanent absence of personnel caused by sickness or other reasons (L: high, I: low)	WP7	For each activity, more than one partner is involved. The consortium is formed with redundant skills and responsibilities.
16	Key personnel disagreeing on strategic choices and/or on IPR/licensing issues (L: low, I: high)	WP7	All The HuT partners have a long experience in working in international and interdisciplinary teams. Disputes relating to WP tasks are responsibilities of the WP leaders, in consultation with the scientific coordination team. IPR/licensing issues will be dealt with by the project management team.

